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Самарканд, Узбекистан**УЛУЧШЕНИЕ КАЧЕСТВА ЖИЗНИ БОЛЬНЫХ ИШЕМИЧЕСКОЙ БОЛЕЗНЮ СЕРДЦА****For citation:** Qilichev A.A., Rizayev J.A. Improving the quality of life of patients with coronary heart disease. Journal of cardiorespiratory research. 2023, vol 4, issue 3, pp.52-57 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10052884>**АННОТАЦИЯ**

В исследование включено 354 пациента с ишемической болезнью сердца (290 мужчин (81,9%) и 64 женщины (18,1%)) в возрасте 36-69 лет (средний возраст $57,7 \pm 7,8$ года), из них 331 в период с января по декабрь 2020. Для сравнения мы проводили безоперационную реваскуляризацию и консервативное лечение по разным показаниям (ЮИК). В зависимости от тяжести УИК и особенностей течения заболевания первоначально проводились консервативные лечебные мероприятия. Затем больным, выздоровевшим после стационарного этапа, было рекомендовано санаторно-курортное лечение.

Ключевые слова: сердечно-сосудистые заболевания, аортокоронарное шунтирование, ишемическая болезнь сердца.**Qilichev Anvar Akramovich**
PhD**Rizayev Jasur Alimdjaniyevich**
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The study included 354 patients with ischemic heart disease (290 men (81.9%) and 64 women (18.1%)) aged 36-69 years (mean age 57.7 ± 7.8 years), of which 331 in the period from January to December 2020. For comparison, we performed non-surgical revascularization and conservative treatment for various indications (NIC). Depending on the severity of the UIC and the characteristics of the course of the disease, conservative therapeutic measures were initially carried out. Then, the patients who recovered after the inpatient stage were recommended sanatorium-and-spa treatment.

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Samarqand, O'zbekiston**YURAK ISHEMIK KASALLIKGI BILAN OG'RIGAN BEMORLARNING HAYOT SIFATINI YAXSHILASH****ANNOTATSIIYA**

Tadqiqotda 36-69 yoshdagi (o'rtacha yoshi $57,7 \pm 7,8$ yosh) yurak ishemik kasalligi bo'lgan 354 nafar bemor (290 nafar erkak (81,9%) va 64 nafar ayol (18,1%)), shundan 331 nafari 2020-yilning yanvaridan dekabr gacha bo'lgan davrda ishtirok etdi. Taqqoslash uchun biz jarrohlik bo'lmagan revaskulyarizatsiya va turli ko'rsatkichlar (NIC) uchun konservativ davolanishni amalga oshirdik. UICning og'irligiga va kasallik kursining xususiyatlariga qarab, dastlab konservativ terapevtik choralar o'tkazildi. So'ngra statsionar bosqichdan so'ng tuzalgan bemorlarga sanatoriy-kurortda davolanish tavsiya etildi.

Kalit so'zlar: yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari, aorta koronar shuntlash, yurak ishemik kasalligi.

In Uzbekistan, as in other developed countries of the world, cardiovascular diseases (CVD) are the main cause of disability (up to 25 percent) and overall mortality (up to 59 percent). Since independence, the population of the Republic has increased from 20 to 33 million people, and the average life expectancy has increased from 66.4 to 73.8 years. It should be noted that cardiovascular diseases have become a major problem due to the increase in the population, and the solution of these problems is the hallmark of health and social policy.

A high level of morbidity, disability and mortality from CVD is a direct threat to public health and leads to significant economic damage [14; 15]. Thus, according to the Federal State Statistics Service (Rosstat), the economic damage from CVD in the Russian Federation is 3.5% of the country's gross domestic product (GDP) - about 12 trillion rubles, which is comparable to government spending on healthcare in the Russian Federation as a whole. At the same time, healthcare costs in Russia are significantly inferior to those in most developed countries (for comparison: in Germany - 8%, Great Britain - 7.5%, France - 8.8%, USA - 7.9%) [8]. Significant economic damage from CVD in conditions of limited healthcare funding determines the relevance of finding effective and cost-effective treatment strategies [19; 21].

However, the potential of CABG to improve the quality of life and prognosis of patients is realized in the postoperative period [3]. According to available data, despite the increase in the number of performed CABG operations and an objective improvement in the condition of the majority (85.6%) of operated patients, only 40-48.6% of them return to work without a decrease in the preoperative level of working capacity and qualifications, due to what is the obvious role of the period of rehabilitation following the operation [2; 10; 12; 13].

Increasing morbidity, high mortality, and annual economic losses associated with a decrease in labor productivity and medical care costs require the development of new directions in the prevention, treatment, and rehabilitation of patients with coronary artery disease [11].

The emergence and development of cardiorehabilitation as a branch of medicine in cardiology is associated with the development in the early sixties of the twentieth century of a system of rehabilitation treatment of patients with myocardial infarction (MI). Using the example of rehabilitation of patients with acute MI, methods of restorative treatment of patients with a cardiological profile, including patients after myocardial revascularization, were scientifically substantiated and tested [9].

Coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG) was first used in the 1960s and quickly became a common procedure in patients with drug-resistant CAD.

For the treatment of severe, rapidly progressing and drug-resistant coronary artery disease, which makes the maximum contribution to disability and mortality, the most promising combination of optimal drug therapy with myocardial revascularization coronary bypass surgery (CABG) [1; 5]. Thus, in the USA the number of these operations per 1 million patients per year is 180, in Europe - 360 (in Sweden - 777). In Russia, more than 3,000 CABG operations are performed annually, and there is every reason to predict that their number will increase.

In Uzbekistan, over the past 10 years, the number of CABG operations has increased by more than 5 times, both due to an increase in the number of institutions (by 26% over the past 5 years) and an increase in the number of operations performed in them [4].

However, surgery is only a stage in the complex treatment of coronary artery disease, and its clinical effectiveness is largely determined by the rehabilitation program aimed at consolidating the achieved results of surgical and conservative treatment [6; 7].

The main components of rehabilitation intervention are adequate drug therapy, physical and psychological rehabilitation, education, and dynamic monitoring of the patient. The high clinical effectiveness of each of the measures of rehabilitation intervention separately can be considered absolutely proven. Participation in rehabilitation programs based on physical training can reduce overall and cardiac mortality by 20% and 26%, respectively ($p < 0.005$), which is comparable to the effect of taking drugs such as aspirin, BAB, ACE inhibitors, statins. Correction of psycho-emotional disorders in the process of psychological rehabilitation significantly improves the psychological

status and quality of life of patients, although it does not affect the prognosis [16]. Data on the clinical effectiveness of cardiorehabilitation (CR), as a long-term complex impact, are single and contradictory [17; 18]. There is no information on the cost and economic efficiency of integrated CI in Uzbekistan, even though labor intensity and high cost are considered as the leading reasons for the insufficient use of CI throughout the world, and today it is not known whether the introduction of complex long-term CI, which increases health care costs, lead to a positive social and economic effect [20; 22]

Material and research methods.

The study included 354 IHD patients (290 men (81.9%) and 64 women (18.1%)) aged 36-69 years (mean age 57.7 ± 7.8 years), 331 of which were between January and December 2020, scheduled CABG was performed. For comparison, we considered 23 patients with coronary artery disease who, for various reasons, did not undergo surgical revascularization and underwent conservative treatment (CHD group).

During the rehabilitation phase, a dynamic examination is carried out:

- at the hospital stage - 354 patients admitted to the cardiology departments of the rehabilitation center in the period from 2018 to 2020.

- at the sanatorium stage - 125 patients who underwent rehabilitation in a sanatorium, of which 95 underwent rehabilitation at a late hospital stage.

- at the outpatient stage - 86 patients.

By the time of the operation, the majority of patients (291 people, or 82.2%) suffered from angina III and IV FC. 36.2% of patients (128 people) were regularly observed by a doctor. The average frequency of visits to a cardiologist is 4.1 ± 1.7 (from 1 to 8) times a year. The majority (55.1%) of all visits to the doctor occurred 3-6 months before admission to the hospital and were associated with preoperative examination and preparation of necessary documents.

In all patients from the onset of coronary artery disease to surgery (including the period of preoperative examination), the total level of cholesterol was determined at least once, and the blood lipid spectrum was determined in 245 patients (69.2%).

Only in 58 (16.4%) patients, total cholesterol was below 4.5 mmol/l; in 62 (17.5%) it was from 4.5 to 5.2 mmol/l; in 126 (35.6%) it was from 5.2 to 6.5 mmol/l; and in 108 (30.5%) it exceeded 6.5 mmol/L.

53.7% (190 people) and 64.7% (229 people) had an elevated LDL content (more than 3.0 mmol/l), and 28.5% (101 people) had an LDL content above 4 mmol/l and 13.0% (46 people) above 5 mmol/l. In 44.9% of patients (159 people), hypertriglyceridemia exceeding 1.7 mmol / l is noted.

A three-stage screening-verification system was used to identify the most common syndrome complexes and plan a rehabilitation program at the hospital stage of rehabilitation.

At the first stage, the actual screening was carried out, which included a survey, examination, study of medical records, determination of the function of respiratory function, a complete blood count, urine, ECG, and the use of a screening electrocardiogram device.

The patients who were included in the study were at the inpatient stage of rehabilitation after surgery and underwent the planned scope of treatment and diagnostic measures.

Within two years, it is planned to carry out 39 mandatory events at the outpatient stage. They consist of five face-to-face consultations with the Center's cardiologist, four intermediate telephone contacts, fourteen activities related to laboratory and instrumental examinations, and sixteen activities related to physical, psychological rehabilitation and patient education programs.

Results and its discussion.

The data on seeking medical care, presented in the relevant lines of the state statistical reporting of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan, are the basis for assessing the incidence of coronary artery disease and its consequences in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Morbidity characterizes the prevalence of the disease in the population, and the availability of medical services, including preventive ones (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Average annual primary incidence of coronary artery disease per 100,000 inhabitants in the regions of Uzbekistan in 2016-2020

Incidence rates continued to rise for five years, as shown in the chart. Surkhandarya and Khorezm regions showed the highest results. In 2016, these figures were 173 and 302 per 100,000 people, but already in 2018 they almost doubled. In Tashkent, the situation is reversed.

Thus, in 2019, the primary incidence of coronary artery disease per 100,000 people decreased by 1.3 times.

The number of deaths from diseases according to the codes I00-I99 of the ICD 10 revision for 12 months was calculated in terms of 100,000 people (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Dynamics of mortality from coronary artery disease per 100 thousand population

The five-year chart shows a 19.7% reduction in CHD mortality. Thanks to the implementation of the orders of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan No 106 dated March 17, 2014 “On improving the provision of diagnostic and therapeutic care to patients with ACS / AMI” and No 422 dated November 17, 2014 “On improving the provision of diagnostic and therapeutic and preventive care to patients with Arterial hypertension” in 2016, there is a decrease in the

overall incidence of coronary artery disease. Since high blood pressure is one of the causes of coronary artery disease, the orders included measures to prevent these diseases.

It is known that chronic heart disease (CHD) can lead to myocardial infarction (MI). According to the US Department of Health Statistics, the number of MI cases for 2021 was 59,280 (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Number of patients with MI for 2021 by regions of Uzbekistan

The regions of Tashkent, Surkhandarya, Kashkadarya, Andijan, Fergana and Tashkent have the highest rates. Of all registered cases of MI, only 22.9% receive inpatient treatment in specialized institutions, such as RRCEM and their branches.

According to the study, the primary disability of adult Uzbeks as a result of IHD decreased by 27.5% from 10.9 to 7.9 per 10,000 people (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Primary disability among the adult population of Uzbekistan due to coronary artery disease for 2016-2020 (per 10 thousand population)

Most of the disabled were in the third group (39.5%), in the second group (32.8%) and in the first group (27.7%) (Fig. 5).

The proportion of disabled people of the first and second groups, respectively, decreased from 28.0 to 22.3% and increased from 33.4 to

29.5% in five years, and the proportion of disabled people of the third group increased from 38.6 to 41.5%. This is due to new high-tech methods of treatment and rehabilitation of patients with cardiovascular

diseases (CVD), which significantly improve functional outcomes in cardiology departments.

Fig. 5. The share of primary disability among the adult population of Uzbekistan due to coronary artery disease for 2016-2020 by group (%)

Thus, over the specified period in Uzbekistan, both an increase and a decrease in the incidence of coronary artery disease, as well as multidirectional fluctuations in the indicator in individual years, were observed.

Conclusions.

Of the 169 patients who worked before CABG, 118 (69.8%) of them underwent MSE during the first year after the operation. 81 (47.9%) of them received confirmation of a disability group, 51.9% were recognized as disabled of group II or III, and 27.5% stopped working. Patients first recognized as disabled were aged 56.4-4.2 years, and 35%

of them suffered any cardiovascular events during the first year after CABG: 9 (5.3%) - MI, 13 (7.7%) - stroke; 26 (15.4%) developed a recurrence of angina pectoris I-II FC, and 12 (7.1%) were hospitalized due to destabilization of the course of hypertension. During the first year, 11 (6.5%) patients (all from group 1) refused to receive disability, and in 2 (4.3%) patients (all from group 1) the disability was removed during the second year. By the end of the first year, the number of patients with group II or III disability after CABG increased to 79.5% (+40% compared to preoperative data), while the number of patients with group 2 disability increased to 100% (+37%) ($p < 0.005$).

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